

EC roadmap towards phasing out of animal testing in chemical safety assessment & change management

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Abstract

The EU roadmap preparation started back in 2023 and has been characterised by a large stakeholder engagement. The final communication on the roadmap will be presented by the European Commission in the first quarter of 2026. This presentation will provide an overview of learnings from the work up to date, and the current planning how to proceed in the implementation phase. The EU policy is already supporting the phasing out of animal testing, so this is much about how to focus efforts, understand what need to be changed to achieve the final goal and how get all stakeholders to buy in, based on their own interests.